

Dating the First Appearance of Mendeleev's Table in a German Textbook

Rammelsberg was, indeed, one of the first of the chemists brought up in the old school to assimilate the new views and to disseminate them.

J. Chem. Soc., Trans., 1901, V79, p7

Thanks to Dr. Pierre-Léonard Zaffalon's remarkable article *Carl F. Rammelsberg and the early diffusion of the periodic table of Dmitri Mendeleev*,¹ we know that it was in the third edition of Rammelsberg's *Grundriss der Chemie gemäss den neueren Ansichten* that Mendeleev's periodic table was first included in a German textbook. My purpose here is to offer a modest addition: although the title page (Fig. 1) states 1873 as the publication year, the book actually appeared in 1872, barely a year after Mendeleev's second canonical article was published in German.²

Figure 1.

¹ Published in *Chemistry: Bulgarian Journal of Science Education*, V26N1, 2017. As of October 2025, it is available online: https://azbuki.bg/wp-content/uploads/chemistry-pdfs/CHEMISTRY_26_1_ZAFFALON.pdf

² *Annalen der Chemie und Pharmacie, Supplement-Band 8*, pp.133-229. The second issue of the eighth supplement was released by the end of 1871.

Such an assertion is based on three pieces of evidence, namely: announcements of forthcoming publications, catalogues of German publishers and lists of received works in journals.

The preface is dated September 1872, which sets the *terminus post quem*. According to earlier ads, such as the one reproduced in Fig. 2 (bound at the end of an essay on the waves of the sea by Karl von Seebach³), the third edition was to be released in September of that year.

Figure 2.

Clearly, the book announced was still in production: “The work will comprise approximately 28–30 *Bogen*,⁴ each costing around 2 *Silbergroschen*”. The final volume contains VI + 415 pages, which make 26 signatures or gatherings.

³ *Ueber die Wellen des Meeres und ihre geologische Bedeutung*. Berlin, 1872

⁴ A printer's sheet, which when folded forms multiple pages.

The book began to appear in catalogues and journals as early as October 1872, the first instance I have found being the entry in the October 10 issue of the trade magazine *Börsenblatt für den deutschen Buchhandel* (Fig. 3).

Figure 3.

Entries in other catalogues that include the page count of the volume are reproduced in Fig. 4: the July-December 1872 issue of *Verzeichniß der Bücher, Landkarten &c.*

Figure 4.

and Fig. 5: the V2N12 issue of *Die Realschule. Zeitschrift für Realschulen, Bürgerschulen und verwandte Anstalten*, under the section: "Writings and maps published from October 31 to the end of December 1872".

Figure 5.

The third edition is mentioned in the November 16, 1872 issue of *Isis*, a Dutch weekly journal, as a new release (Fig. 6).

Figure 6.

The final evidence is the mention in the October 24, 1872 issue of *Nature* as a book received (Fig. 7).

Figure 7.

As a matter of fact, it was not uncommon for certain books to have title pages printed with the next year's date, presumably for marketing reasons. For instance,

searching for 1873 in the 1872 edition of *Verzeichniß der Bücher, Landkarten &c.* reveal almost 50 more cases, all of them appearing in the second semester (Fig. 8).

Figure 8.

It is worth noting that such a dating quirk did not occur in the fourth edition of *Grundriss der Chemie*, which has 1874 on both the title page and the preface page (dated November). A likely, though perhaps indirect, explanation is that the third edition had been approved for use in upper secondary schools by an Austrian Ministerial decree of July 23, 1874.⁵

As an aside, I described a related case in *Dating the First Periodic Table in Spanish Textbooks: The Case of Mascareñas*,⁶ where the year on the title page was also misleading.

Figure sources

1. From my collection. Available on Google Books: <https://books.google.es/books?id=cRoNAAAAAYAAJ>
2. From my collection. Available on Google Books: <https://books.google.es/books?id=irhSAAAAcAAJ>
3. Available online: https://digipress.digitale-sammlungen.de/view/bsb11034665_01315_u001?page=4,5
4. Available online: <https://www.digitale-sammlungen.de/en/view/bsb11039572?page=744,745>
5. Available on Google Books: <https://books.google.es/books?id=p2x1y8kSm8UC>
6. From my collection. Available on Google Books: https://books.google.es/books?id=hPA_AQAAMAAJ
7. *Nature* 6, 528 <https://doi.org/10.1038/006528a0> Also: <https://books.google.es/books?id=9qMzAQAAMAAJ>
8. Screen capture of Google Books: <https://books.google.es/books?id=MKwEAAAAQAAJ&q=1873>

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⁵ *Verordnungsblatt für den Dienstbereich des Ministeriums für Kultus und Unterricht*. Vienna, 1874

⁶ Available on my blog: <https://jordihidalgo.blogspot.com/2025/05/mascarenas.html>